

Model development for microchannel reactor systems for the production of hydrogen by methanol steam reforming

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Abstract

The present study is directed to the model development for a parallel reaction system, especially a chemical processing micro-system, which can simultaneously carry out exothermic and endothermic reactions in separate micro-channels and simultaneously adjust feed composition and flow rates. Specifically, the present study relates to the model development for a catalytic process of steam-methanol reforming for the production of hydrogen in a microchannel heterogeneous reaction system. Computational fluid dynamics simulations are performed with respect to various factors pertaining to microchannel reactor systems. Steady-state analyses are carried out to investigate the effects of various key parameters on processes such as chemical reactions or heat and mass transfer in the system. To facilitate computational modeling of transport phenomena and chemical kinetics in the flowing system of complex chemical reactions involving gas-phase and surface species, steady-state analyses are performed and computational fluid dynamics is used. The boundary conditions relate macroscopic fluid flow at a catalytically active surface to the rates of surface reactions. Chemical reactions involving surface species significantly influence the boundary conditions. The mass fluxes of gas-phase species at the phase boundaries are balanced by the production rates of gas-phase species by surface reactions. The heat release and consumption due to a surface reaction must be included in the model. Endothermicity or exothermicity of surface reactions contribute to the energy balance at an interface. Heat fluxes in the solid phase are balanced by chemical heat release at the surface. The porous media model is applied to the computational domains of the catalytically active layers. The porous media involve surface reactions. Each porous medium is modeled by adding a momentum source term to the standard momentum conservation equations and by the modification of a heat conduction flux term to the standard gas phase energy balance equation. The predictions are in satisfactory agreement with the data obtained from experimental measurements.

Keywords: Microchannel reactors; Transport phenomena; Chemical kinetics; Endothermic reactions; Catalytic processes; Steam reforming

1. Introduction

Microchannel reactors for chemical processing provide significant advantages over conventional chemical processing technology including improved heat and mass transfer [1, 2]. Due to these advantages, microchannel processing and microchannel reactors have been a topic of intense interest for many years [3, 4]. A major problem is that the cost of microchannel reactors continues to hinder the use of microchannel processing. Cost is a particularly important for high temperature applications in which devices are often made of expensive materials such as the superalloys.

A microchannel is a channel having at least one internal dimension (wall-to-wall, not counting

catalyst) of 10 millimeters or less (preferably 2.0 millimeters or less) and greater than one micron (preferably greater than 10 microns), and in some embodiments 50 to 500 microns; a microchannel remains within these dimensions for a length of at least one centimeter, preferably at least 20 centimeters. Microchannels are also defined by the presence of at least one inlet that is distinct from at least one outlet. Microchannels are not merely channels through zeolites or mesoporous materials [5, 6]. The length of a microchannel corresponds to the direction of flow through the microchannel. Microchannel height and width are substantially perpendicular to the direction of flow of through the microchannel. The value of the Reynolds number describes the flow regime of the stream [7, 8]. While the dependence of the regime on Reynolds number is a function of fluid velocity, fluid properties, and microchannel cross-section size and shape.

Currently, endothermic reactions performed in microchannel reactors are driven using heat from an external source, such as the effluent from an external combustor [9, 10]. In doing so, the temperature of the gas stream providing the heat is limited by constraints imposed by the materials of construction [11, 12]. For example, a typical microchannel reactor constructed from Inconel 625 might be limited in use for gas service to temperatures of about 1050 °C or less. Practically, this means that the effluent from an external combustor must be diluted with cool gas (i.e., excess air) to bring the gas temperature down to meet material temperature constraints [13, 14]. This increases the total gas flow rate, raising blower and compressor costs [15, 16]. Moreover, heating the gas stream externally introduces heat losses (associated with delivery of the hot gas to the microchannel reactor) and expensive high temperature materials to connect the combustor to the microchannel reactor.

An integrated combustor can produce heat for the reaction in close proximity to the reaction zone, thus reducing heat losses and increasing efficiency [17, 18]. Because traditional combustion catalysts are not stable at high temperatures (above about 1200 °C) due to noble metal sintering, the integrated combustor must remove heat at a rate sufficient to keep local temperatures at the catalyst surface below this level or risk rapid catalyst deactivation. In an integrated reactor, combustion or heat generation should occur in close proximity to the endothermic reaction. Preferably, an exothermic reaction occurs in microchannels that are interleaved with microchannels in which there is an endothermic reaction [19, 20]. Co-flow of endothermic and exothermic reaction streams is preferred; however, cross-flow or countercurrent flow is also an option. The heat of an exothermic reaction is conducted from the exothermic reaction catalyst to the endothermic reaction catalyst, where it drives the endothermic reaction. This rapid heat removal from the combustion region enables the option to use a very small fraction of excess air. The use of a flow-by catalyst configuration for one or both the exothermic and endothermic microchannels can create an advantageous capacity-pressure drop relationship.

Despite extensive study of the process of steam reforming in micro-structured chemical reactors, the effects of different factors on efficiency and performance have not been well studied. Further study is needed to effectively increase the catalyst's efficiency while reducing catalyst requirements. The present study is directed to the model development for a parallel reaction system, especially a chemical processing micro-system, which can simultaneously carry out exothermic and endothermic reactions in separate micro-channels and simultaneously adjust feed composition and flow rates. Specifically, the present study relates to the model development for a catalytic process of steam-methanol reforming for the production of hydrogen in a microchannel heterogeneous reaction system. Computational fluid dynamics simulations are performed with respect to various factors pertaining to microchannel reactor systems. Steady-state analyses are carried out to investigate the effects of various key parameters on processes such as chemical reactions or heat and mass transfer in the system. The objective is to develop a model for microchannel heterogeneous reaction systems. Particular emphasis is placed on the model development for a catalytic process of steam-methanol reforming for the production of hydrogen in a microchannel heterogeneous reaction system.

2. Physical models

The study relates to a catalytic process for the production of hydrogen by steam reforming of methanol, in which methanol and steam are reacted in a microchannel reactor under relatively high pressure. Steam reforming of methanol have attracted much attention for applications in fuel cells. The reforming process proceeds in one set of the channels through which the endothermic reactants flow, and the exothermic oxidation process proceeds in the second set of the channels. Exothermic and endothermic reactions take place simultaneously whereby the heat required for the latter is supplied by the former. Heat transfer occurs via conduction through the walls of the reactor. For the endothermic reaction, the structure is especially effective because both the internal surfaces of the walls are coated with structured catalysts, which is capable of providing more efficient heat exchange and minimizing the problem of loss of catalytic activity. The term "structured catalyst" refers to a catalyst supported on a structure, typically a fabricated metal or ceramic structure.

The autothermal reactor is configured for simultaneous oxidation and steam reformation of methanol. The reactor system comprises two separate sets of flow channels, which are located between spaced, highly heat-conductive metal or ceramic separating walls. The medially located, bi-catalytic separating walls have different catalysts on opposed surfaces. These catalysts are selected for the particular reaction taking place in the adjacent reaction zone. The reactor provides for continuous and simultaneous reaction of two different process reaction streams in the channels defined between the walls, wherein a first process reaction stream undergoes a high temperature exothermic reaction in the first set of flow channels and a second process reaction stream undergoes an endothermic heat-consuming reaction in the second set of flow channels separated from the first set of flow channels by the heat transfer separating walls. More specifically, the reactor system includes a set of reforming channels for steam reformation of methanol and a set of oxidation channels for heating the reactor system to operating temperature. A separating wall therefore separates two adjacent reaction zones and also functions to transfer heat from the oxidation occurring at the catalyst surface in the oxidation zone directly to the reforming catalyst coated on the opposed surface. There are multiple possibilities for the arrangement of the oxidation channels and the reforming channels for heating, such as co-current, countercurrent, or cross-flow modes. In the present study, the two separate sets of flow channels are arranged in a co-current flow configuration.

The reactor system is operated using excess air and water steam. Methanol and air are mixed homogeneously and the mixture is fed directly into the oxidation channels in a specific ratio. Preferably, excess water steam is provided to the reactor to increase efficiency and to maintain operability, for example, to prevent carbon formation [21, 22]. Such a reactor system is typically adiabatic in nature, meaning no heat is added in addition to the exothermic reaction heat release. The reactor system offers relatively simple designs and operation. The reactor system is in the form of a catalytic coating on a substrate composed of ceramic or metal walls defining straight reforming or oxidation channels which are parallel to each other and to the axis of the reactor. Relatively high mass transfer is provided by using high cell density channels, namely low hydraulic diameter channels. The design increases the number of boundary layers between a fluid and a reactor wall by a factor of one hundred or more, and boundary layers are known to impede heat transfer. However, relatively high heat transfer is provided.

Water steam is converted into hydrogen-rich gas using methanol in an endothermic reaction on a catalyst. The energy which is released during catalytic oxidation is necessary for the endothermic steam reformation taking place simultaneously. Methanol is combusted catalytically with air, and the heat released is used to heat the reactor. There is even less need for mass and volume storage capacity, since the same alcohol fuel is used for the endothermic and exothermic processes. An array of channels operating in parallel is used, and the inside of the channels is coated. All channels are of the same

cross-section and length. Additionally, there are equal numbers of oxidation and reforming channels, which are arranged in an alternating pattern. The wall of each channel is composed of a substrate coated with a catalyst. The substrate is preferably metal, and most preferably stainless-steel sheet.

The ratio of the height of the channels to the width of the channels may vary. In the present study, the cross-sectional configuration of the channels is square. The channels are 0.7 millimeters in height and in width and 30.0 millimeters in length. Channel height refers to the inside height of a channel. To ensure the mechanical strength at elevated pressures, the thickness of the uncoated walls and the catalysts is 0.7 and 0.1 millimeters, respectively. The oxidation catalyst consists essentially of oxides of copper, zinc and aluminum. The oxidation catalyst allows for initial start-up and the heat-up of the reactor system. The reforming catalyst consists essentially of copper and oxides of zinc and aluminum. The exothermic and endothermic processes are conducted at a pressure of 0.8 megapascals, with a methanol-air equivalence ratio of 0.8 and a steam-to-methanol molar ratio of 1.17. The inlet temperature of the mixtures is 373 degrees Kelvin. The temperature of the reactor can be regulated by the balance of the flow rates so that the catalyst is not overheated by the exothermic process and thus damaged. To assure that adequate temperatures are provided for endothermic reforming, operating flow conditions are specified for the reactor by giving the gas velocity. The gas velocity is 2.0 meters per second at the reforming channel inlets and 0.6 meters per second at the oxidation channel inlets, thereby assuring sufficient heat in the reactor to carry out endothermic reforming of methanol.

3. Mathematical models

To facilitate computational modeling of transport phenomena and chemical kinetics in the flowing system of complex chemical reactions involving gas-phase and surface species, steady-state analyses are performed and computational fluid dynamics is used. ANSYS FLUENT is applied to the problem involving surface chemistry. ANSYS FLUENT handles thermodynamic properties, transport properties, gas-phase equation-of-state, and chemical kinetics.

Chemical species can exist in the gas phase or on surface sites. A nomenclature is introduced to facilitate manipulating species information so that the terms can be defined and used in a self-consistent manner. Two types of species are defined: gas-phase and surface. The first type is a species in the gas phase above the surface, which is annotated in a reaction by the symbol g . The number of gas-phase species is denoted by the symbol K_g . A surface species is defined to be the chemical species at the gas-solid interface, which is denoted by the symbol s . A surface does not necessarily have to be flat, and each surface species occupies one surface site. A site is considered to be a position or location on the surface at which a species can reside. A site does not necessarily have a composition itself or have to be a particular atom, and the total number of sites per unit area is conserved. Therefore, the sum of the site fractions of the species on the sites is unity. The total number of surface species is designate by the symbol K_s . The total number of species is designate by the symbol K .

The total number of species in each reaction mechanism is given by

$$K = K_g + K_s . \quad (1)$$

To facilitate manipulating phase information, a multicomponent gas mixture is denoted by the symbol m , and a solid wall is denoted by the symbol w .

The Reynolds numbers are very small so that the gases flow through the channels in a laminar flow regime. The conservation equations are presented below for each gas phase.

The gas phase mass balance is stated as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u_x)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_y)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_z)}{\partial z} = 0 . \quad (2)$$

The variables in this expression are the coordinate variables x , y , and z , gas-phase mass density ρ , and velocity u .

The momentum conservation equations are given by

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{2}{3} \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_{zx}}{\partial z} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} \right) \right] = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{2}{3} \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_{zy}}{\partial z} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} \right) \right] = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\frac{2}{3} \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial z} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) \right] = 0 \quad (5)$$

with p being the pressure and μ being the dynamic shear viscosity.

The gas phase energy balance is stated as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u_x h)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_y h)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_z h)}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\rho \sum_{g=1}^{K_g} Y_g h_g V_{g,x} - \lambda_m \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\rho \sum_{g=1}^{K_g} Y_g h_g V_{g,y} - \lambda_m \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\rho \sum_{g=1}^{K_g} Y_g h_g V_{g,z} - \lambda_m \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

The variables in this expression are the gas-phase enthalpies h_g , gas-phase mass fractions Y_g , thermal conductivity λ , temperature T , and gas-phase species diffusion velocities V_g .

The contribution of homogeneous chemical reactions involving gas-phase species is insignificant under the conditions of interest [23, 24]. The conservation equation for chemical species can be written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u_x Y_g)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_y Y_g)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_z Y_g)}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\rho Y_g V_{g,x}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\rho Y_g V_{g,y}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho Y_g V_{g,z}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

The gas-phase diffusion velocity \vec{V} can be written as follows:

$$\vec{V}_g = -D_g^m \nabla \left(\ln \left(\frac{Y_g \bar{M}}{M_g} \right) \right) + \left(\frac{D_g^T M_g}{\rho Y_g \bar{M}} \right) \nabla (\ln T), \quad (8)$$

wherein the mean molar mass is denoted by \bar{M} is, the molar mass of species g is denoted by M_g , and D^T and D^m is the thermal and molecular diffusivity, respectively.

The gas-phase mass fractions must sum to one

$$\sum_{g=1}^{K_g} Y_g = 1. \quad (9)$$

Mass conservation requires that the sum of the diffusion fluxes is zero

$$\sum_{g=1}^{K_g} Y_g \vec{V}_g = 1. \quad (10)$$

The gas-phase equation-of-state is given by

$$p = \frac{\rho RT}{M}. \quad (11)$$

where R is the ideal gas constant.

The equation for conservation of energy is presented here for the solid walls:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_w \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\lambda_w \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\lambda_w \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = 0. \quad (12)$$

A surface reaction mechanism is assumed to involve K_s chemical species with I surface reactions. This reaction mechanism can be represented in the following general form

wherein χ_s is the chemical symbol for surface species s , ν_{si} is the stoichiometric coefficient for surface reaction i with surface species s , which is positive for both reactants and products, ν'_{si} is the stoichiometric coefficient described for reactants, and ν''_{si} is the stoichiometric coefficient described for products.

The production rate \dot{s}_s for each of surface species can be written as a sum over the rate-of-progress variables for all reactions involving surface species s :

$$\dot{s}_s = \sum_{i=1}^I \nu_{si} q_i, \quad (s = 1, \dots, K_s), \quad (14)$$

$$\nu_{si} = \nu''_{si} - \nu'_{si}, \quad (15)$$

where the chemical production rate of surface species s is denoted by \dot{s}_s , and the rate-of-progress variable for surface reaction i is denoted by q_i .

The rate-of-progress variable for surface reaction i is given by the difference of the forward rates and the reverse rates as follows:

$$q_i = k_{fi} \prod_{s=1}^{K_s} [\chi_s]^{\nu'_{si}} - k_{ri} \prod_{s=1}^{K_s} [\chi_s]^{\nu''_{si}}, \quad (16)$$

wherein $[\chi_s]$ is the molar concentration of surface species s , k is the rate constant, k_{fi} is the forward rate constant of surface reaction i , and k_{ri} is the reverse rate constant of surface reaction i .

The forward rate constant of surface reaction i as a function of thermodynamic temperature is given by the modified Arrhenius expression as follows:

$$k_{fi} = A_i T^{\beta_i} e^{\frac{-E_i}{RT}}, \quad (17)$$

in which A_i is the pre-exponential factor of surface reaction i , β_i is the dimensionless temperature exponent of surface reaction i , and E_i is the activation energy of surface reaction i .

The reverse rate constant of surface reaction i involved in reaching equilibrium is related to the forward rate constant through the equilibrium constant, which has the following form:

$$k_{ri} = \frac{k_{fi}}{K_{ci}}, \quad (18)$$

in which K_{ci} is the equilibrium constant of surface reaction i . The equilibrium constant is given in concentration units.

The conservation equation is presented here for surface species:

$$\frac{\theta_s \dot{s}_s}{\Gamma} = 0, \quad (s = 1, \dots, K_s), \quad (19)$$

where the coverage is denoted by θ , and the active site density is denoted by Γ .

The boundary conditions on heat and mass flux are discussed below. These boundary conditions relate macroscopic fluid flow at a catalytically active surface to the rates of surface reactions.

Heterogeneous reactions at a catalytically active surface affect the heat and mass balance at the surface. In addition, surface reactions create sources and sinks of chemical species on the surface and in the gas phase. Consequently, chemical reactions involving surface species significantly influence the boundary conditions. The mass fluxes of gas-phase species at the phase boundaries are balanced by the production rates of gas-phase species by surface reactions. The boundary condition concerning the surface species balance at the phase boundaries takes the following form:

$$\eta \beta M_g (\dot{s}_g)_{\Delta} + (\rho Y_g V_{g,y})_{\Delta} = 0, \quad (g = 1, \dots, K_g), \quad (20)$$

$$\eta \beta M_g (\dot{s}_g)_{\Delta} + (\rho Y_g V_{g,z})_{\Delta} = 0, \quad (g = 1, \dots, K_g), \quad (21)$$

where η is the effectiveness factor and β is the surface area factor. The phase boundaries are denoted by the subscript Δ .

The heat release and consumption due to a surface reaction must be included in the model. Endothermicity or exothermicity of surface reactions contribute to the energy balance at an interface. Heat fluxes in the solid phase are balanced by chemical heat release at the surface. The boundary condition concerning the energy balance at the phase boundaries can be written as follows:

$$k_s \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{\Delta^+} + k_s \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right)_{\Delta^+} - k_g \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{\Delta^-} - k_g \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right)_{\Delta^-} + \sum_{g=1}^{K_g} (\dot{s}_g h_g M_g)_{\Delta} = 0, \quad (22)$$

wherein \dot{s}_g is the chemical production rate of gas-phase species g through adsorption or desorption in heterogeneous catalysis. In this expression, the energy released or consumed at each phase boundary is obtained using a summation over all gas-phase species.

The surface area factor is defined in terms of geometric and catalyst surface area by the formula

$$\beta = \frac{A_c}{A_g}, \quad (23)$$

where A_c is the catalyst surface area and A_g is the geometric surface area. Geometric surface area is the macroscopic surface area of a substrate that holds or supports a catalyst in a reactor. Geometric surface area does not include the additional surface area contributed by generally microscopic or small surface roughness or porosity. Catalyst surface area refers to the surface area of the kinetically active substance in a catalytic reactor.

The effectiveness factor is given by the Thiele modulus Φ as

$$\eta_g = \frac{\dot{s}'_g}{\dot{s}_g} = \frac{\tanh(\Phi)}{\Phi}, \quad (24)$$

wherein \dot{s}' refers to the effective production rate. Species i is denoted by the subscript i . The Thiele modulus for the chemical reactions can be expressed using the following equation:

$$\Phi = \delta \sqrt{\frac{\gamma \dot{s}_g}{c_g D_g}}, \quad (25)$$

wherein δ is the thickness of a catalyst substrate, γ is the catalyst specific surface area, c is the surface concentration, and D is the effective diffusivity.

Catalyst specific surface area is a property of substrates, defined as the catalyst specific surface area divided by the volume of the substrate that holds or supports a catalyst in a reactor

$$\gamma = \frac{A_c}{V_c}, \quad (26)$$

in which V_c is the volume of a catalyst substrate.

The porous media model is applied to the computational domains of the catalytically active layers. The porous media involve surface reactions. The dependence of the effective diffusivity on porosity and tortuosity factor can be expressed using the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{D_g} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_p} \tau_p \left(\frac{1}{D_g^m} + \frac{1}{D_g^K} \right). \quad (27)$$

in which ε_p is the porosity, τ_p is the tortuosity factor, and D^K is the Knudsen diffusivity. The porosity is isotropic. The porosity does not vary with space and therefore the porous media are homogeneous.

For the sake of simplicity, it is assumed that substantially all the pores have a similar diameter. In this scenario, the diffusivity for Knudsen diffusion depends on the mean pore diameter d_p , given by

$$D_g^K = \frac{d_p}{3} \sqrt{\frac{8RT}{\pi M_g}}. \quad (28)$$

Each porous medium is modeled by adding a momentum source term to the standard momentum conservation equations described above. The source term is composed of two parts: a viscous loss term and an inertial loss term. The source term S_i for the momentum equation along i direction can be written as follows:

$$S_i = - \left(\frac{\mu}{\alpha} v_i + C_2 \frac{1}{2} \rho |v| v_i \right), \quad (29)$$

in which α is the permeability, v is the superficial velocity, v_i is the superficial velocity along i

direction, and C_2 is the inertial resistance factor.

The superficial velocity can be represented as

$$v = \varepsilon_p u. \quad (30)$$

Each porous medium is modeled by the modification of a heat conduction flux term to the standard gas phase energy balance equation described above. In each porous medium, an effective thermal conductivity is used for the heat conduction flux.

The effective thermal conductivity of the catalyst layer is computed as follows:

$$\lambda' = (1 - \varepsilon_p) \lambda'_s + \varepsilon_p \lambda_g, \quad (31)$$

in which λ' is the effective thermal conductivity, and λ'_s is the solid medium thermal conductivity.

4. Chemical kinetic models

The equation for the catalytic oxidation reaction can be denoted as follows:

wherein the standard molar enthalpy of reaction is denoted by $\Delta_r H_m$.

Methanol can be catalytically reformed according to the following equation:

Methanol can be catalytically decomposed to hydrogen and carbon monoxide in accordance with the following equation:

In order to convert carbon monoxide into carbon dioxide, a further water-gas shift reaction is needed [25, 26]. The water-gas shift reaction can be denoted as follows:

Therefore, the reformat provided from the reactor is enriched in hydrogen.

The rate of the methanol-steam reforming reaction r_R is expressed by partial pressures

$$r_R = \left[k_R K_{\text{CH}_3\text{O}^{(1)}}^* \left(p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) \left(1 - k_R^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2}^3 p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{-1} \right) C_{S_1}^T C_{S_{1a}}^T \right] \cdot \left[\left(1 + K_{\text{CH}_3\text{O}^{(1)}}^* \left(p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) + K_{\text{HCOO}^{(1)}}^* p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} + K_{\text{OH}^{(1)}}^* \left(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) \right) \left(1 + K_{\text{H}^{(1a)}}^{0.5} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} \right) \right]^{-1}, \quad (36)$$

wherein the total surface concentration of site i is denoted by $C_{S_i}^T$, the composite parameter and the species adsorbed on active site i are represented by the superscript $*$ and (i) , respectively, and the species index is represented by the subscripts 1 and $1a$.

The rate of the water-gas shift reaction r_W is given by

$$r_W = \left[k_W^* K_{\text{OH}^{(1)}}^* \left(p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) \left(1 - k_W^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{CO}}^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{-1} \right) C_{S_1}^{T^2} \right] \cdot \left[\left(1 + K_{\text{CH}_3\text{O}^{(1)}}^* \left(p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) + K_{\text{HCOO}^{(1)}}^* p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} + K_{\text{OH}^{(1)}}^* \left(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) \right) \right]^{-2}. \quad (37)$$

The rate of the methanol decomposition reaction r_D is given by

$$r_D = \left[k_D K_{\text{CH}_3\text{O}^{(2)}}^* \left(p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) \left(1 - k_D^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2}^2 p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}^{-1} \right) C_{S_2}^T C_{S_{2a}}^T \right] \cdot \left[\left(1 + K_{\text{CH}_3\text{O}^{(2)}}^* \left(p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) + K_{\text{OH}^{(2)}}^* \left(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right) \right) \left(1 + K_{\text{H}^{(2a)}}^{0.5} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} \right) \right]^{-1}, \quad (38)$$

wherein the species index is represented by the subscripts 2 and 2a.

5. Numerical algorithms

To obtain the solution of the problem, numerical simulations are performed using computational fluid dynamics. The problem is solved using structured meshes. The mesh is refined in the computational domains of the catalytically active layers. A mesh independence study is carried out. The solution is independent of the mesh resolution. Numerical simulations are performed within ANSYS FLUENT using computational fluid dynamics [27, 28]. Boundary conditions are specified and physical properties are defined for the fluids, solids, and mixtures. Physical properties depend on temperature and composition. A piecewise-polynomial function is specified for the temperature dependence. To define composition-dependent properties for the mixtures, the mass-weighted-mixing-law is applied.

The mathematical formalism developed to describe transport phenomena and chemical kinetics is implemented into ANSYS FLUENT. The computer code and its usage are fully documented. More specifically, ANSYS FLUENT is applied to define the terms in the equations relating to conservation, thermodynamics, chemical production rates, and equation of state, and then combine the results to define the problem involving surface chemistry. To describe the surface reaction mechanisms in symbolic form, the following information is required, including the thermochemical properties of surface species in the surface phases, names of the surface species, site densities, names of all surface phases, Arrhenius rate coefficients, reaction descriptions, and any optional coverage parameters.

The governing equations described in detail above are solved numerically for the conservation of mass and momentum and for energy and species. The governing equations are discretized in space, and the second-order upwind discretization scheme is used. The pressure-based segregated algorithm is used with SIMPLE-type pressure-velocity coupling. The under-relaxation factors are reduced for all variables. The residuals decrease by at least six orders of magnitude to at least 10^{-6} . Overall heat and mass balances are achieved and the net imbalance is less than one percent of smallest flux through the domain boundaries. The solution to the problem converges when the residuals reach the specified tolerance and overall property conservation is satisfied.

6. Model validation

A general and flexible framework is provided above for describing the model involving complex transport phenomena and chemical kinetics. Predetermined boundary conditions may be necessary in order to exactly matches the specifications or requirements. To verify the accuracy of the model, the predictions are compared with the data obtained from experimental measurements. The channels are rectangular in cross section. The channels have a length of 33.0 millimeters, a height of 0.6 millimeters, and a width of 0.5 millimeters. The reactor operates with a steam-to-carbon molar ratio of 1.1, and hydrogen is produced by steam reformation at a specific temperature. The temperature of the

endothermic process stream ranges from 473 to 533 degrees Kelvin. In the steam reformation facility, the catalyst support is brought to operating temperature using electrical heating means. The measured temperature profile serves as the thermal wall boundary conditions. Accordingly, the model described above is modified by the predefined wall boundary conditions. The predictions are in satisfactory agreement with the data obtained from experimental measurements.

7. Conclusions

The present study is directed to the model development for a parallel reaction system, especially a chemical processing micro-system, which can simultaneously carry out exothermic and endothermic reactions in separate micro-channels and simultaneously adjust feed composition and flow rates. Specifically, the present study relates to the model development for a catalytic process of steam-methanol reforming for the production of hydrogen in a microchannel heterogeneous reaction system. Computational fluid dynamics simulations are performed with respect to various factors pertaining to microchannel reactor systems. Steady-state analyses are carried out to investigate the effects of various key parameters on processes such as chemical reactions or heat and mass transfer in the system. The objective is to develop a model for microchannel heterogeneous reaction systems. Particular emphasis is placed on the model development for a catalytic process of steam-methanol reforming for the production of hydrogen in a microchannel heterogeneous reaction system.

To facilitate computational modeling of transport phenomena and chemical kinetics in the flowing system of complex chemical reactions involving gas-phase and surface species, steady-state analyses are performed and computational fluid dynamics is used. ANSYS FLUENT is applied to the problem involving surface chemistry. ANSYS FLUENT handles thermodynamic properties, transport properties, gas-phase equation-of-state, and chemical kinetics. The boundary conditions relate macroscopic fluid flow at a catalytically active surface to the rates of surface reactions. Chemical reactions involving surface species significantly influence the boundary conditions. The mass fluxes of gas-phase species at the phase boundaries are balanced by the production rates of gas-phase species by surface reactions. The heat release and consumption due to a surface reaction must be included in the model. Endothermicity or exothermicity of surface reactions contribute to the energy balance at an interface. Heat fluxes in the solid phase are balanced by chemical heat release at the surface. The porous media model is applied to the computational domains of the catalytically active layers. The porous media involve surface reactions. Each porous medium is modeled by adding a momentum source term to the standard momentum conservation equations. Each porous medium is modeled by the modification of a heat conduction flux term to the standard gas phase energy balance equation. The predictions are in satisfactory agreement with the data obtained from experimental measurements.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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